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Status of Stack & System Development at Sunfire

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Abstract

Sunfire develops and produces high-temperature fuel cell (SOFC), electrolyzer (SOEC) and co-electrolysis (Co-SOEC) systems. SOFCs convert fuels and gases into electricity and heat for various applications. SOECs and Co-SOECs convert water and/or CO₂ with preferably renewable electricity into hydrogen or syngas. With these technologies, Sunfire addresses a multitude of challenges in our energy system.

To be able to satisfy the needs of those varying products, Sunfire's SOC technology is continuously being improved on stack as well as on system integration level to achieve the optimal balance between high reliability, low manufacturing costs and high electrical efficiency.

In this publication, an update of the results of our long-term stack tests will be presented (new tests with our present stack design as well as updates of our long runners).

This will be followed by showing the next steps of the scale-up and automation of our production volumes.

Finally, an update of the status of our SOFC products for residential CHP (Sunfire-Home) and offgrid power (Sunfire-Remote) and SOEC (Sunfire-Hylink) as well as Co-SOEC (Sunfire-Synlink) applications will be given. Here the status of ongoing projects and next steps will be discussed.

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Introduction

Sunfire develops and produces high-temperature fuel cell (SOFC) and electrolyzer (SOEC) systems. SOFCs convert fuels and gases into electricity and heat and SOECs convert water and/or CO₂ with preferably renewable electricity into hydrogen or syngas. With these technologies, Sunfire addresses a multitude of challenges in our energy systems.

The company was founded in 2010 by a team of experienced entrepreneurs and engineers. Sunfire has ~150 employees and is backed by Paul Wurth, Neste, idinvest Partners, Inven Capital and Total Energy Ventures as well as private investors.

Sunfire started with the production of stacks and small systems mainly for residential CHP (Sunfire-Home) and off-grid power applications (Sunfire-Remote) with outputs of less than 1 kW per unit. SOEC development started in 2012. Stacks, stack modules and systems have been successfully tested at ambient and pressurized conditions. [1] In 2014 first rSOC stack tests were performed, followed by a complete system development in cooperation with Boeing and during the GrInHy project. [2,3]

By expanding the product portfolio to hydrogen and syngas production (Sunfire-Hylink, Sunfire-Synlink), larger modules up to 150kW SOEC power input have been developed. These modules are also implemented in the megawatt scale SOEC systems that will be operated starting 2020 in the framework of GrInHy2.0 and MultiPLHY and are the basis for all future large pilot plants.

To be able to satisfy the needs of those varying products, Sunfire's SOC technology is continuously being improved to achieve the optimal balance between high reliability, low manufacturing costs and high electrical efficiency.

In this publication, results of our recent stack development will be shown followed by an update on the scale-up of our production volumes as well as a short update on the status of our various products.

1. Stack Development

Sunfire's stack design is based on a planar, parallel-flow design with an open cathode which is optimized to achieve an ideal tradeoff between cost, performance, and degradation. It is an electrolyte supported (ESC) design with Crofer 22 APU as metal cassette, a Ni/GDC hydrogen electrode, a 3YSZ electrolyte and an LSCF oxygen electrode. It is developed to run in SOFC as well as in SOEC and Co-SOEC mode and is robust to thermal as well as redox cycles. In the following chapters, updates on the degradation results and improvements will be shown.

Long term test in SOFC mode.

Sunfire is continuously long-term testing its stacks in SOFC and SOEC mode. In Figure 1 the evolution of the ASR of a SMK-B230-type stack, which is tested alongside with another stack in a double stack test (each stack with 30 cells), operated for 23kh in SOFC mode is shown. The ASR is corrected to the fuel conversion polarization and temperature fluctuations. The BOL-ASR is ~650 mΩ cm²/kh and the linear degradation rate is ~17 mΩ cm²/kh in the first half and ~11 mΩ cm²/kh in the second half of the stack test.

This suggests a decreasing degradation rate over time that also is accordance with known ageing mechanisms and verifies the general feasibility of Sunfires stack design over long operating times.

Figure 1. ASR evolution of a 30 cell stack during SOFC operation at 0.226 A/cm² with H₂ as fuel.

Even though a lot of test bench failures with associated thermal cycles happened during this test, as can be seen by the little spikes in the ASR in Figure 1, no signs of cell breakages or other anomalies are present. The test is ongoing.

Degradation/long term tests in SOEC mode.

The ASR and degradation during SOEC operation for the recently approved SMK-B240-design [7] with a 30-cell stack operated at Sunfire is displayed in Figure 2.

Figure 2. ASR evolution of 30 cell stack during SOEC operation at current densities varying from -0.25 to -0.65 A/cm². The linear degradation is 21 mΩ cm²/kh.

As in the previous chapter, the ASR is corrected to the fuel conversion polarization. Furthermore, the stack ASR is temperature corrected to be able to see the material degradation itself. Because if the temperature correction is omitted, the resulting ASR-degradation is virtually zero because the existing material degradation is blurred by the ASR decrease due to the increasing operation temperature in the SOEC thermoneutral mode.

The initial ASR is $\sim 525 \text{ m}\Omega \text{ cm}^2$ and thus lower than the values reported for the SOFC-mode ($\sim 650 \text{ m}\Omega \text{ cm}^2$) due to thermoneutral operation that leads to a uniform temperature profile instead of the steep temperature profile that is observed in SOFC mode.

The calculated total ASR-degradation is $\sim 21 \text{ m}\Omega \text{ cm}^2/\text{kh}$ for the complete test which included endothermal, slightly exothermic and mainly thermoneutral operation phases as well as various cycles (thermal, hot-standby and redox). The degradation of purely stationary operation was observed to be as low as $10 \text{ m}\Omega \text{ cm}^2/\text{kh}$ (e.g. from 4500 to 5000 h). The post-test-analysis revealed a small, however, relevant silicon contamination of the H₂ electrodes which is believed to be a major cause of the SOEC operation. If this contamination can be eliminated, lower degradations comparable to the SOFC degradation reported in the previous chapter or to the degradation of cell tests [6] or for SOFC modes of the SMK-B240 design [7] are to be expected.

Degradation/long term tests in Co-SOEC mode

A 30 cell stack operated in Co-SOEC mode is presented in Figure 3 showing the evolution of the stack ASR and the stack temperature. The current density is 0.59 A/cm^2 with a conversion rate of 70% and a gas composition of H₂O/CO₂/H₂/CO=60/30/7/3 aiming at a H₂/CO ratio of approx. 2 in the produced syngas. The mean linear degradation amounts to $22 \text{ m}\Omega \text{ cm}^2/\text{kh}$ as indicated by the dashed line in Figure 3 which is similar to SOEC operation with steam. (At 1800 h the stationary operation was interrupted by a thermal cycle due to an increase in the SiO₂ contamination which was reduced for the subsequent operation leading to a jump in ASR which was ignored for the calculation of stationary degradation values) In the post-test-analysis no damages or issues related to the Co-SOEC such as carbon deposition have been observed after the stationary operation. Again, small amounts of Si were found in the H₂ electrode leading to an increased degradation rate as also described in the previous chapter.

All the results shown in this chapter verify that, if silica contaminants can be avoided, the Sunfire cell and stack design can be operated in SOFC, SOEC, as well as CO-SOEC with low degradation rates and without any issues. Therefore, it is a solid foundation for Sunfire-Home and -Remote as well as Sunfire-Hylink and -Synlink systems.

Figure 3. ASR evolution of a 30 cell stack during Co-SOEC operation with a mean degradation of 22 mΩ cm²/kh.

2. Industrial Scale-Up

To be able to fully industrialize our technology, the costs of the stacks need to be decreased further. This can either be done by changing the materials used within the stack or by implementing fully automated processes and scaling up the stack production. Sunfire is continuously working on both of those means. In this chapter, we will show 2 newly designed devices to increase production capacity and decrease the costs of the production step.

Automated MCF-WPS coater

To enhance the capacity and reduce the costs of our spray coating process an automated WPS-coater has been developed and produced. It has a cycle time of 10s per interconnect to be able to achieve approx. 60 MW SOEC output capacity per year and can be integrated in a fully automated production line if needed. Furthermore, it decreases the working time per stack by approx. 90 minutes and thus the costs significantly.

The device has already been tested preliminarily and will be put into full operation until end of October. (c.f. Figure 4)

Figure 4. Automated MCF-WPS coating device

Automated Stacking device

In addition to the coater also an automated stacking device is currently under development. There, one stack shall be produced in a cycle time of less than 10 minutes. Also the stacking device can later be integrated into a fully automated production line and reduces the stacking time by approx. 130 minutes. Additionally, scrap rates will be decreased because manual stacking errors can be avoided.

The device is currently being designed and shall be put into operation in mid-2021.

3. Update on Product Development

Sunfire Home

After the takeover of new enerday GmbH by Sunfire GmbH in autumn 2018 our site in Neubrandenburg Germany, operates under the name Sunfire Fuel Cells GmbH. It is now advancing a joint platform technology for micro-CHP devices for residential buildings and off-grid power supplies.

With Sunfire-Home, Sunfire Fuel Cells is introducing an add-on micro-CHP solution for supplying electricity and heat to single-family homes with natural gas as fuel as well as with LPG for homes, that are not connected to public gas grid and offer an attractive option to replace boilers based on heating oil with a more environmentally friendly, efficient and innovative system.

The **Home 750** offers a rated electrical output of 750 W and a thermal output of 1,300 W. In addition to reducing emissions, the advantages of Sunfire-Home include high efficiency, fully automatic operation with remote access and simple integration with modern building technology such as a peak load boiler and a hot water storage tank.

As part of the PACE market launch program, funded by the Fuel Cells and Hydrogen Joint Undertaking (FCH JU) with Horizon 2020, the first 500 devices will be placed on the market.

At Sunfire Fuel Cells the series production for Sunfire Home with a capacity of 500 units per year was started. The first units are shipped to costumers and are in operation (Figure 6)

Figure 5. Small scale series production at Sunfire Fuel Cells and first installed customer systems in operation

Sunfire Remote

Looking at Sunfire-Remote, Sunfire Fuel Cells promotes a compact SOFC-system for self-sufficient and off-grid power supply from pipeline gas and Propane. The units can be integrated in trailers or enclosures as well as in hybrid systems with batteries and photovoltaic panels. Typical applications include the power supply of measuring and control equipment for oil and gas pipelines, air traffic signal lighting of wind farms in the construction phase and the mobile power supply for security systems and telecommunications stations.

Figure 6. Sunfire-Remote unit used as power supply for wind farms in the construction phase

The Sunfire-Remote **R400** units are battery chargers primarily and provide continuous power for a wide range of applications with an average power consumption up to 400 W. Load changes and peaks, also in the kilowatt range, can be covered by batteries that has to be selected according the needed capacities and specific requirements. Based on Sunfire's SOFC-technology the systems are perfectly suited for reliable, durable and independent off-grid power supply. Fueled by LPG/Propane or natural gas, they reach electrical efficiencies of up to 35 %. Due to the lack of combustion, they provide clean power with minimal noise.

Based on the **Home750** platform, Sunfire will introduce a larger off-grid system in 2020, called **R900**, with up to 900 W DC power per unit.

Sunfire Hylink/Synlink

Today, Sunfire is the leading provider of HTE systems worldwide, quickly moving into the multi-megawatt market for industrial applications. By focusing on the utilization of industrial off-heat to maximize overall electrical efficiency, the operational cost for continuous hydrogen production can be kept at a minimum. With an electric consumption of ≤ 3.7 kWh/Nm³H₂ approximately 30 % more product can be produced with the same electricity input compared to legacy technologies such as PEM and alkaline electrolysis. Sunfire units are therefore specifically suited for brown-field industrial applications, as demonstrated at the steel plant of Salzgitter, where a 730 kWAC HTE system is currently being installed within the GrInHy2.0 project, after successfully operating a 150 kWel,AC rSOC system since 2017. For more detailed information on the Sunfire SOEC product and the scale-up plan, please refer to [5].

Figure 7. 1 MW HTE plant with power electronics container (blue) and dry cooler (grey) comprising 4 Generation 2 Sunfire-HyLink or Sunfire-SynLink Modules.

In addition to pure hydrogen electrolysis (SOEC or Sunfire-HyLink), Sunfire is also developing the Co-SOEC (Sunfire-SynLink) providing renewable syngas, a mixture of H₂ and CO, for chemical applications and so-called Power-to-Liquid processes. The operation has been successfully demonstrated within the Kopernikus PtX project. Now the scale-up to industrial scale is next with the development of a Generation 2 HTE Module (Figure 7). The new module contains 60 stacks in a single housing and will be able to operate both in hydrogen electrolysis and co-electrolysis mode. This development strategy will ensure rapid scale-up of both product lines at once. The Generation 2 Module will provide a net production rate of more than 75 Nm³/h hydrogen or syngas at a nominal power of approx. 300 kWAC at drastically cut manufacturing costs. It will enable HTE systems to reach a capacity of several MW and to be competitive on the electrolysis market. A first demonstration of the Gen2 will be a 2.5 MW Sunfire-HyLink plant at the Neste refinery in Rotterdam (Netherlands) within the EU funded MultiPLHY project [5]. A first Synlink pilot plant will be demonstrated on large scale by Sunfire's daughter company Norsk e-Fuel in Heroya (Norway) starting with 20 MW SynLink capacity to produce 10 million liters synthetic fuel per year in 2023

4. Summary and Outlook

Sunfire reaches low degradation values over several thousand hours (as shown in this contribution for at least 23kh in SOFC; 9kh in SOEC and 3.5kh in CO-SOEC) with its stack design. The industrial scale up of the production line up to 60MW a year is ongoing by continuously introducing automated devices leading to further decreased stack costs.

Sunfire's products are also continuously being improved. Sunfire Fuel Cells has scaled up its production capacity to 500 Sunfire-Home systems a year and already shipped the first units to customers in Germany. Furthermore, the 400 W Sunfire-Remote is available while the larger 900W unit will be introduced in 2020.

Within the project GrInHy2.0, Sunfire will install the first long-term demonstration units of an SOEC-system (Sunfire-Hylink) on megawatt scale at an iron and steel plant (GrInHy 2.0) and a refinery (MultiPHLY). In addition to that, Sunfire has also already shown that renewable syngas can be produced with its technology and will install a 20 MW SynLink / PtL plant in Heroya (Norway) in 2023.

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References

- [1] O. Posdziech, K. Schwarze, J. Brabandt, Efficient hydrogen production for industry and electricity storage via high-temperature electrolysis, Intern. J. of Hydrogen Energy, Volume 44 issue 25, pages 19089-19101 2019.
- [2] J. Mermelstein and O. Posdziech, Fuel Cells, Development and Demonstration of a Novel Reversible SOFC System for Utility and Micro Grid Energy Storage, Volume 17, issue 4, pages 562-570, 2017.
- [3] K. Schwarze, O. Posdziech, J. Mermelstein, S. Kroop, Operational Results of an 150/30 kW RSOC System in an Industrial Environment, Fuel Cells, Volume 19, issue 4, Pages 374-380, 2019
- [4] C. Geipel, K. Herbrig, F. Mittmann, M. Pötschke, L. Reichel, T. Strohbach, A. Surrey, C. Walter, Stack Development and Industrial Scale-Up, EFCF 13; A0303, (2018)
- [5] O. Posdziech, T. Geißler, K. Schwarze, R. Blumentritt, System Development and Demonstration of Large-Scale High-Temperature Electrolysis, ECS Transactions SOFC-XVI, 2019
- [6] J. Schefold et. al., 80,000 current on/off cycles in a one year long steam electrolysis test with a solid oxide cell, Intern. J. of Hydrogen Energy, Volume 45, issue 8, pages 5143-5154, 2020
- [7] C. Geipel et. al., Stack Development and Industrial Scale-Up, ECS Transactions SOFC-XVI, 2019

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